

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL IN COUNTERING CYBERCRIME

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In today's world, cybercrime poses a serious threat to global security and economic stability. As A.A. Bessonov noted, "Modern cybercrime is a serious threat both to individual states and to the entire world community" [1.231]. Unlike traditional crimes, which are often limited by geographical boundaries, cyber attacks can be carried out from anywhere and exploit vulnerabilities in a country's digital infrastructure. In order to counter cybercrime, it is necessary to establish cooperation between law enforcement agencies of the countries. However, achieving effective international cooperation is challenging due to various obstacles such as legal differences, jurisdictional issues, technological challenges and geopolitical tensions.

As K.K. Klevtsov rightly noted, "Most law enforcement agencies, when investigating cybercrimes, intentionally or without intent, resort to the practice of obtaining evidence physically located on the territory of other states independently, without obtaining the consent of these states. This happens by remotely connecting in real time to a subscriber device of a criminally prosecuted person or removing such a device from a victim or witness located in the territory of the State whose law enforcement agencies are conducting proceedings on a cybercrime case, followed by an inspection to find information relevant to the case, as well as by using other legal methods" [2.1]. However, in order for this issue to be resolved without violating national sovereignty, it is necessary to establish international cooperation, but this issue still remains open due to a number of reasons. As noted by Hazel Diez Castaño, head of the information security office at Banco Santander, "Cybercriminals have an advantage on the battlefield: it is easier to attack than to defend, since protection requires more effort and resources. Therefore, the public and private sectors must work together to develop collective information on cyber threats and to share detection, security and technology tools, as well as coordinated incident response mechanisms. By joining forces and creating specific channels of

cooperation, we will be able to achieve a decisive shift in the fight against cybercrime" [3.1].

International cooperation in the fight against cybercrime is complicated by the divergence of positions of different states of the world, due to basic differences in approaches to defining concepts, the lack of a clear understanding of the boundaries between various phenomena requiring different mechanisms of cooperation, differences in approaches to ensuring the security of personal data, the general level of mutual distrust, which makes it impossible to cooperate on cross-border procedural partnership.

With regard to cybercrime, there is the following paradox: "on the one hand, States are forced to cooperate to combat such a transnational threat as cybercrime, but, on the other hand, such cooperation affects the sovereignty of the State, limits it in the field of criminal law and information protection. Therefore, cooperation is successful in regions with a high level of political trust between countries, as it happens in the European Union" [4.38].

S. Brenner noted that "it is known that it is possible to effectively counteract cybercrime only by joining forces. This is exactly the path taken by the world's largest Internet service providers, who in 2005 announced the conclusion of a global anti-hacker alliance, within which an early warning system for hacker attacks on the Internet was created" [5.218]. In addition, in 2011, the International Cybersecurity Alliance was established in London, designed to combat cybercrime on a global scale [6.1].

Despite various attempts by countries or individual organizations to create any advantage over cybercriminals, their efforts remain in vain, as confirmed by the results of the study "in 2023, the number of ransomware attacks increased by 160% compared to the previous year" [7.1].

As some scientists have noted, "the legal analysis of international cooperation and national legislation of various states indicates the absence of a unified practice in combating cybercrime" [8.2], despite the existence of a number of multilateral treaties on this issue, which, of course, negatively affects this area of activity of states [9.2].

There are many challenges associated with international cooperation and the development of international guidelines to combat cybercrime. Identifying criminals across borders anywhere in the world, as well as conducting investigations and securing electronic evidence, is in itself a difficult task. As noted by Russell G. Smith "one of the important results of the very few successful cases is an unprecedented demonstration of multilateral international

cooperation between law enforcement agencies, the exchange of information and evidence collection techniques, identification of violators and their arrest. Nevertheless, this level of cooperation is the exception rather than the rule" [10.2].

"Considering the factor of globalization of computer crime, it becomes more obvious that today no state is able to independently counter this threat. At the same time, an essential role in such cooperation belongs to international legal mechanisms for regulating and interacting with law enforcement agencies on countering and investigating computer crimes" [11.225].

As K. Klevtsov noted, "international cooperation in the field of criminal proceedings in the field of cybercrime should be optimized by regulating at the national level the timely provision of responses to requests for legal assistance, since during pre-trial proceedings in this category of criminal cases, traditional mechanisms of cooperation prevail within the framework of multilateral or bilateral agreements or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity" [12.1]. It is worth noting that the use of traditional forms of cooperation leads to the loss of important information and the disclosure of cybercrimes due to lack of efficiency.

Thus, international cooperation is a key point in eliminating the legal vacuum that exists between the development of information technologies and the response of legislation to them. The process of developing measures at the international level, as experience shows, is in itself a complex problem. However, this is the only way to reliably protect against electronic attacks.

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